

The Effects Of The International Monetary Fund Loans On The Iraqi Government Performance : 2016 Loan As A Model

Hayder Zuhair Jasim, Saad Abdul Hussein Naama

Article Info

Article History

Received:
Month, 2020

Accepted:
March 10, 2020

Keywords

Development, Iraq's
Sovereign, economy

Abstract

Iraq has witnessed events and developments that affected all its political, economic and social aspects as a result of the weak Iraqi government performance in investing wealth and capabilities that abound in the geographical nature since 2003 and up to the current situation. Partisanship away from the national interest, plunging the country into successive crises, weakening the joints of the state and deepening sectarian and ethnicity among the Iraqi people, and all these imbalances led to patchy solutions for the purpose of containing the major crises, including the air A to external loans to fill the deficit in the state budgets over the past years, so the study focused on the IMF loan that it granted to Iraq in 2016 as a model for measuring the Iraqi government performance, while providing some solutions and proposals to address the loan crisis.

Introduction

Iraq was severely affected by the war against ISIS in 2014, as well as the sharp drop in oil prices, which account for 90% of Iraq's financial imports, as well as the aftermath of the war from the destruction of cities and the displacement of citizens and the purchase of military requirements, equipment and weapons, which drained the country's resources and caused a crisis Significant financial balance of payments, which prompted Iraq to borrow domestic and foreign loans from various institutions such as the World Bank, international development institutions and others as well as the International Monetary Fund, which is the subject of this study.

Therefore, the importance of the study comes from the fact that it addresses a vital issue related to loans that are as inputs to the economic process that contributes to the rotation of capital between the creditor and the debtor and results in an economic movement towards a particular sector or several sectors at the same time, In addition to their role in resolving the crises that the economies of countries are experiencing as a result of internal or external causes, in this study we will focus on the IMF loan to Iraq in 2016 to identify the feasibility of the loan and its impact on the Iraqi economy and government performance.

methodological framework for the research

1. Study hypothesis:

The study was based on the premise that external loans restrict the performance of government work in a positive way, i.e. loans have a positive (temporary) impact that establishes negative repercussions in the future. This is what the study will try to prove.

The problem of the study:

The problem with the study lies in the nature of the loans themselves, the loans are the same, but the methods of their investment vary from country to country depending on the effectiveness and strength of the political system and its democracy, which determines the feasibility and usefulness of the loan. So the study will try to answer the following questions:

- What are the IMF's mechanisms for granting loans?
- What are the lending tools?
- What is a special drawing right?
- What are Iraq's rights to withdraw?
- How has the Iraqi government performed in dealing with loans?
- How did the loan affect government performance?
- What is the future of Iraq under the loan policy?

3- Research objectives: The research aims to:

- Explaining the reasons for Iraq's recourse to foreign loans.
- The study aims to show the effectiveness and feasibility of the 2016 loan in dealing with the crises that Iraq went through at that stage.
- Provide a program of work or a road map through which the accumulated loans to Iraq can be repaid and economic development and thus the national interest of Iraq.

Methodology adopted:

The study relied on the inductive approach through data collection and observation of the phenomena associated with the loan in order to link a set of issues that accompanied the loan process and its impact on government performance, and the fact that the study of loans is (part of all) i.e. that the loan process is part of the economy, that is, the loan process is part of the economy and it is all and this is what this approach focuses on, as well as the development of a set of conclusions based on observations, estimates, and experiences. that would get us to the research objectives.

5- The structure of the study:

The study was divided into three themes, in the first axis the mechanisms for granting the IMF loans, first the process of lending in the IMF, secondly the instruments of lending, and thirdly the right of special withdrawal. The second theme is the reflection of the loan on the performance of the government, and the first guaranteed the mechanism of granting the loan to Iraq, secondly the terms of the loan granted to Iraq, thirdly the objectives of the loan, and fourthly the reflection on the performance of the government, while the last theme was the future of Iraq in the light of the trend towards borrowing ending with conclusions and recommendations, As well as the proposed program of work on this study.

The first theme/ mechanisms for granting the IMF loans

The IMF is a global organization with 189 countries founded to improve the integrity of the global economy, which aims to promote global monetary cooperation, ensure financial stability, facilitate international trade, and encourage increasing employment opportunities, sustainable economic growth and poverty reduction around the world, and all member countries are represented on its Executive Board, which discusses the effects of each country's economic policies at the national, regional and global levels and approves loans to help member states in addressing temporary problems facing the balance of payments. The Fund focuses on three key roles:

-To advise member states on adopting the necessary policies to achieve economic stability, accelerate economic growth and reduce poverty.

Funding available to member countries to help them address balance of payments problems.

-Providing technical assistance and training at the request of Member States to strengthen the expertise and institutions necessary to implement peaceful economic policies.

-Provide funding to member states to assist them in addressing balance-of-payments problems.

First / lending process in the fund

The International Monetary Fund provides its resources at the request of member countries, and this is usually done under a loan agreement that may provide, depending on the lending instrument used, specific economic policies and measures that the concerned country agrees to implement to resolve the balance of payments problem. The member state, in consultation with the Fund, determines the economic policy program on which the agreement is based, and in most cases submits it to the Executive Board under the "Letter of Intent", and after the Executive Board approves the agreement, the fund's required resources will be disbursed and are usually divided in instalments. Progress consistent with progress in the implementation of the program. However, some agreements allow countries with very strong performance to take advantage of the Fund's resources in advance at once, and are therefore not subject to explicit policy understandings.*

Second. loan tools from the Fund

Loans are a major source of budget deficit financing and are used to mobilize savings and finance public spending.† When tax policy cannot cover the increased growth in public expenditures, the country resorts to it.

Unlike development banks, IMF does not provide loans to finance specific projects, but to member states facing balance-of-payments problems to give them time to correct economic policy and restore growth without having to resort to actions that harm themselves or economies other members, fund funding is intended to help member states address balance of payments problems, achieve economic stability and restore sustainable economic growth.‡

The various lending instruments used by the Fund are designed to accommodate the different types of balance-of-payments needs (actual, expected, or potential; short- or medium-term), as well as the different circumstances of the member countries. Low-income countries can borrow on concessional terms through the facilities available under the (PRGT) (and loans on concessional terms are available at zero interest until the end of 2016), and high-income countries are lent non-concessional loans with interest.

• Non-concessional lending

The tools used by the Fund to provide loans on normal terms are "credit standby agreements" and by-stand ("SBA - "Arrangements" and "Flexible Credit Line") "Line Credit Flexible" and "Extended Fund Facility", and facilitate the Fund Extended (Precautionary and Liquidity Line - "PLL") (EFF) plus emergency assistance through the "Instrument Financing Rapid" ("RFI" to assist member countries whose balance of payments are in

urgent need. The fund for the prevailing interest rate in the market, known as the "fee rate", while an additional fee receives large loans that exceed certain limits, and the "fee rate" is determined by the interest rate on Special Drawing Rights which is reviewed weekly to take into account changes in short-term interest rates in the markets Major international criticism. The maximum amount of loan a member country may obtain from the fund, known as "resource utilization limits", varies depending on the type of loan requested.[§]

• **Concessional Lending**

The new concessional lending facilities for low-income countries were repaired in 2010 with the support of the Trust growth and Reduction Fund ("PRGT"). Revised in 2013 in a broader effort to make the Fund's financial support more flexible and relevant to the different needs of low-income countries). In 2015, the criteria and utilization limits for concessional facilities were expanded in order to maintain their levels in proportion to increased production, trade, and capital flows. Thus, the terms of financing have become easier, interest rates are reviewed once every two years and are 0% until the end of 2016.) All funding facilities support the programs adopted by the countries concerned with a view to achieving a viable macroeconomic center consistent with growth and poverty reduction on a strong and lasting basis.**

Third. the right to Special Drawing

The right of Special Drawing is an international reserve asset developed by the Fund in 1969 to complement the official reserves of member countries. By April 2016, 204.1 billion SDRs (equivalent to US\$285 billion) had been introduced and distributed to member countries. The SDR can be exchanged for any freely usable currency. The value of the right of Special Drawing is determined by a basket of five major currencies - the Chinese yuan, the US dollar, the euro, the Japanese yen and the British pound - as of October 1, 2016.^{††}

The role of the Special Drawing right in the International Monetary Fund

The Fund established SDRs in 1969 as an international reserve asset, in the context of the Bretton Woods fixed exchange rate regime. The country participating in the system needed official reserves - gold holdings by the Government, the Central Bank or widely accepted foreign currencies - which could be used to purchase its domestic currency from foreign exchange markets to the extent necessary to maintain its national exchange rate. However, international supply of two of the most important reserve assets - gold and the US dollar - proved inadequate to support the expansion of world trade and financial flows at the time. The international community has thus decided to establish a new reserve asset under the auspices of the International Monetary Fund.

A few years after the creation of the right of Special Drawing, the Bretton Woods system collapsed and the major currencies were converted into floating exchange rate regimes. Consequently, borrowing has become easier for creditworthy Governments thanks to the growth in international capital markets, and many countries have large volumes of international reserves.

These developments have led to a decline in reliance on the right of private withdrawal as a global reserve asset. But the 182.6 billion-unit SDR, distributed in 2009, recently played an important role in providing liquidity to the global economic system and complementing member states' official reserves in the midst of the global financial crisis. The SDR is neither a currency nor a maturity on the Fund. It is a potential entitlement to freely usable currencies of member countries. SDR holders can obtain these currencies for their own SDR holders in one of two ways; The first method is to agree on voluntary exchanges among member states, and the second is to entrust the Fund to members with strong external positions to purchase SDRs from member countries with weak external positions.^{‡‡}

B. A basket of currencies that determines the value of the withdrawal right

The SDR was initially valued at 0.888,671 grams of pure gold - which at the time was also equivalent to US\$1. After the collapse of the Bretton Woods system in 1973, Special Drawing Rights (SDR) was redefined as a basket of currencies. As of October 1, 2016, the SDR basket consisted of the Chinese yuan, the US dollar, the Japanese yen, the euro and the pound sterling. The value of special drawing rights is determined against the United States dollar and published daily on the Fund's website.

This value is calculated on the basis of the total amounts per currency in the basket in United States dollars, using the exchange rates announced at noon each day in the London market. The Executive Board reviews the basket components every five years, or earlier if the Fund considers that the circumstances have changed to justify an early revision, in order to ensure that they are a correct reflection of the relative currency importance in the international trading and financial system. In the last review (concluded in November 2015), the Executive Board decided to consider the Chinese yuan as a freely usable currency and included in the SDR basket. The US dollar is estimated at 41.73%, the euro at 30.93%, the Chinese yuan at 10.92%, the Japanese yen at 8.33%, and the British pound at 8.09%. These weights were used to determine how much of each of the five

currencies was included in the new SDR basket. The next review is scheduled by the end of September 30, 2021.^{§§}

C. Special Drawing Rights interest rate

The interest rate on SDRs is the basis for the calculation of interest on member countries' loans and interest due for their use of their resources in regular (non-concessional) fund loans; It also represents the interest paid to members for their own SDR holdings, which are paid for their allocations of these rights. The SDR interest rate is set weekly and is based on a weighted average of the interest rates represented on short-term debt instruments in financial markets where currencies that make up the SDR basket trade.^{***}

Distributing Special Drawing Rights allocations to member countries

Under its constituent agreements (Article 15, Section I and Article 18), the Fund may distribute special drawing rights allocations to member countries in proportion to its membership quotas. This distribution allows each member country to obtain an international reserve asset at no cost or conditions. The SDR mechanism is self-financing, charging distribution fees that are subsequently used to pay interest on SDR holdings. If a member country does not use any of its Special Drawing Rights holdings, the fees are equal to the interest received.

If the Member Country's Special Drawing Rights (SDR) exceeds the amount allocated to it, it acquires actual benefits over the excess amount. Conversely, if he or she has less possession than this allocation, he or she will have to pay interest on the amount of the shortfall. The Fund's articles of agreement also allow for the abolition of Special Drawing Rights, but this provision has never been used. The Fund's articles agreement provides for the adoption of certain types of official organizations, such as the Bank for International Settlements, the European Central Bank and regional development banks. As other Holders of Special Drawing Rights - i.e. non-members of the Fund. The approved holder may obtain special drawing rights and use them in transactions and operations with other holders and with members of the Fund. The Fund may not allocate special drawing rights to itself or to accredited holders. The general distributions of Special Drawing Rights must be based on a long-term global need to supplement available reserve assets. Decisions on public distributions are made at successive core intervals of up to five years. Although these distributions were made only three times, the first with a total value of 9.3 billion units distributed in 1970-1972 and the second with 12.1 billion units distributed in 1979-1981, The third, with a value of 16.2 billion SDRs, was distributed on August 28, 2009. The fourth amendment to the Convention entered into force on 10 August 2009, which provided for a special allocation of the Special Drawing Rights to be made only once, at the value of 21.5 billion special drawing rights units. The purpose of the amendment was to enable all members of the Fund to participate in the SDR system on a fair basis and to correct the conditions of the countries that joined the Fund after 1981 – which represented more than one fifth of the current membership – since they had no distribution before 2009. Both the public and private distribution for 2009 raises the cumulative total distribution to 204.1 billion units.^{†††}

E. the purchase and sale of special drawing rights

Member states often need to buy special drawing rights to use to pay their obligations to the Fund, or they may want to sell them to adjust the composition of their reserves. The Fund may act as a mediator between members and certified holdings to ensure that the SDR can be exchanged for freely usable currencies. The SDR market has worked for more than two decades past through voluntary swap agreements. Under these agreements, a number of member countries and an accredited holder were volunteering to sell and purchase SDRs within the limits of the relevant agreements.

Following the distribution of SDRs in 2009, these agreements were expanded in number and size in order to ensure the continued liquidity of the SDRs voluntary trading market. The number of optional SDRs swap agreements now stands at 32, of which 19 have been new since the SDR distribution in 2009. Since September 1987, voluntary transactions have ensured the liquidity of SDRs. However, if the possibilities under the optional swap agreements are not sufficient, the Fund could begin to activate the mechanism of commissioning under which member states with sufficiently strong external positions are charged with purchasing special drawing rights from members with weak external positions in exchange for freely usable currencies. However, the transaction value does not exceed certain limits. This arrangement contributes to a supportive role that ensures the liquidity of the SDR and the distinctive character of its role as a reserve asset.^{†††}

The second thesis/the effect of loans on the Iraqi governmental performance

First, the mechanism of granting the loan to Iraq

The IMF board approved a three-year credit-readiness loan to Iraq after Iraq's request and with special drawing rights of 3,831 billion units (i.e. approximately \$5.34 billion or 230%). With an interest of 1.5% paid in five years, to support the Iraqi government's economic reform program, after Iraq presented the letter of intent that was submitted to the Fund's executive board and approved, and that the Council's approval enabled the disbursement of 455 million SDRs (\$634 million). In July 2016, Iraq received a payment according to the rapid Financing Tool, equivalent to one million SDRs (1.24 billion) at the time of ratification.^{§§§}

Iraq became a member of the Fund on December 27, 1945, with a membership of 1,663.80 million Special Drawing Rights (SDR) (2.32 billion US dollars).

Second: Conditions of the loan granted to Iraq:

The IMF has linked the loan to a number of conditions, including the following:^{****}

1. The Iraqi Government shall take measures to reduce expenditures in the State budget for fiscal year 2016 by 13 trillion dinars.
2. Take measures to settle the dues of oil companies and not allow them to accumulate.
3. To subject the entire salary and allowances to senior state employees and higher and special job grades to income tax, the tax ranges from 7.5% to 15% of the total salary and allowances.
4. Rehabilitation or restructuring of publicly funded self-financing companies.
5. To work hard to improve the performance of the financial and regulatory bodies in the country and at all levels and to impose strict control on the exchange doors of this loan.
6. To inform the IMF of Iraq's real net exchange during 2015.

Agreement is required Iraq issues the Financial Management Act, the inclusion of the integrity Authority as an effective party to the follow-up process and the adoption of the United Nations Anti-Corruption document.

Mr. Prime Minister's advisor Dr. Mazher Mohammed Saleh stated that the agreement with the Fund does not indicate the allocation of a share of the loan to the Kurdistan Region, and that the region has required the federal government to obtain 15% of the foreign loans obtained by Iraq. The chancellor also confirmed that the agreement was transparent, no secrets or secrets regarding the loan.

How to act on the loan amount and verify its expenditure on the purposes for which it was originally allocated, and to achieve the main objectives envisaged, the burden of implementation and follow-up will be primarily on the international parties involved and supporting this agreement and not on the Government of Iraq alone.

Third/loan objectives

For the sake of executing the loan, a program was set according to the agreement between Iraq and the fund aiming at achieving stability in the Iraqi economy that was damaged by two clashes, namely the sharp drop in oil prices and the war against ISIS, and the agreed program focused on four sections:^{†††}

1- Dealing with external pressures, including maintaining the exchange rate as the main pillar in this regard, gradually removing currency restrictions, strengthening the fight against money laundering and countering terrorist financing to stop the demand and illegal speculation on foreign exchange.

2- Implementing financial support and protecting the poor at the same time: by reducing inefficient capital spending while protecting social spending, this would encourage spending to a sustainable level given the significant reduction in oil revenues and the government will work to formulate deeper reforms in revenues Expenditures and their implementation in order to support the initial non-oil budget and achieve debt sustainability.

3- Strengthening public financial management and combating corruption: In order to improve financial discipline and spending efficiency, the Ministry of Finance will strengthen the legislation of public finance management, prepare financial report tables in accordance with international standards, strengthen compliance controls, manage cash and conduct surveys. And regular scrutiny in order to prevent payment arrears.

4- Monitoring financial risks in order to maintain the stability of the public sector: Important steps have been adopted in order to strengthen the legal framework of the Central Bank of Iraq after evaluating the guarantees made by the fund and restructuring the banks of the state and strengthening the standards of precautionary and banking supervision with support In addition, measures will need to be implemented to prevent money laundering, combat terrorist financing and strengthen anti-corruption legislation to help integrate Iraq's financial system into the global economy.

Fourth/ Reflection on government performance

The reversal of this loan, according to members of parliament and members of the government, is positive on fiscal policy as it gave it the opportunity to expand at a difficult time, oil revenues were low, as well as the fact

that Iraq was in a military confrontation with ISIS and was in dire need of open funding to sustain the momentum of the war.

The experience of the past decade has shown that the consensual model of State administration is characterized by the absence of economic vision and weak policies for economic reform and development of its agricultural, industrial and service sectors, waste resources and deepening structural imbalances by sustaining the oil resource's momentum in financing the budget, economy and unemployment. He did not take into attention the seriousness of linking the economic and financial fate of the country to a resource linked to external factors. Thus, international institutions can help design a new economic framework that is commensurate with the realities of the Iraqi economy and limits the corrupting burden of the country in controlling oil resources away from development and stability.^{****}

The repayment of the loan represents a great burden on the national economy, which is basically a deduction from the purchasing power of individuals and their consumer and investment demand, and that before obtaining an external loan, Iraq has to plan in advance in the investment of this loan. The first step they take here should be to borrow funds commensurate with their productive capacity, i.e. they should invest the loan funds in expanding production so as to provide the foreign currency from which they can benefit in the payment process when the repayment is due, and the export policy can be adopted in order to provide foreign currency. The loan must invest in the production of exportable goods. This is certainly not easy, as Iraq must calculate the resilience of external demand for the goods it exports.

There is also a policy of compensation for imports, in the sense that the country produces alternative goods than it previously imported, which also means the provision of foreign exchange earnings. The accumulation of external indebtedness and the inability to pay also have obvious negative effects on the balance of payments, in which case the balance of payments will be in Iraq's favor, which will have a negative impact on the entire national economy.

The third thesis/ the future of Iraq in light of the trend towards loans

Loans are very useful during crises, but continued borrowing generates an accumulation of public debt rates, which is a burden on future budgets, especially if they are not invested in productive sectors from which the financial return comes from the repayment of the loan, and borrowing increases the government's laziness in maximizing non-oil revenues and the addiction to borrowing in financing the budget. Loans also have negative effects on citizens as the state and in order to repay loans tend to tax goods and services as happened in the 2016 budget.

This depends on the quality of government performance, meaning the applicability of the performance quality standards set by the World Bank, as the more Iraq moves away from these standards, the more corruption is described (corruption) and the higher rate of corruption in the country, the higher the rate of corruption there, these standards are openness and transparency, the political stability, the effectiveness of government performance in providing services, the organizational structures. Rule of law and control of corruption.

The diagnosis of the effects of external borrowing on the Iraqi economy is based on two points: The first point is the conditions related to the loan, both in terms of interest and the size of the annual installments needed to repay the loan principal and in terms of the conditions set by the international institutions, i.e. the International Monetary Fund, as a prelude to obtaining the borrowing, which are the risk of the Iraqi economy being subjugated to the international institutions and losing its independence. The lower the interest rate and the lower the size of the annual payments, the more the Iraqi economy is able to face external borrowing and its service and the opposite is true, but what happened in this loan is that the interest of the loan was very low, as it did not exceed 1.5%. The loan repayment period has also been set within five years but after three years as a grace period, i.e. the loan is not repaid once the country receives the loan and is allowed to start repaying the loan after three years. It also accounts for 7% of GDP, which means that it falls within the optimal size of public debt. The second point, which is the activities to which external borrowing is directed, are they investment (capital) or consumption (operational) activities? If the loan is directed toward investment activities, it will lead to reviving the Iraqi economy by activating idle sectors such as agriculture, industry, conversion, tourism and others, and building tax containers that can bear the tax burden to face the origin and benefits of the loan, but if the loan is directed toward consumption activities, inflation will be even slightly higher. On the other hand, the problem of the loan directed toward consumption activities is not to build a reliable production base on which to repay the loan and its benefits at the time of repayment.

Conclusion

The loans represent a big burden that burdens the countries and undermines their economy in the long term, especially if the country does not take successful and investment mechanisms to repay loans and not accumulate

them. What is happening in Iraq is that loans continue in the budgets approved by the parliament, which indicates that there are no means and solutions to deal with this phenomenon and that they continue their influence on the Iraqi economy. We note that in a 2016 loan, the Iraqi negotiator was able to succeed in gaining profits for Iraq in a difficult record and needed quick financing in the light of the crises that occurred at that stage. But the biggest problem remains in the total debts Iraq suffers because of the unsuccessful policies that Iraq inherited from the previous regime, especially the commitments imposed by the Security Council on Iraq, the compensations from the occupation of Kuwait and other debts of the Gulf countries and another country.

The debts that Iraq accumulated due to the governments' policies after 2003, which were not successful in managing the country's economic file, increased Iraq's suffering in its burden of additional debts that reached more than 131 billion dollars without finding a real and effective treatment for its repayment. We therefore present the conclusions, recommendations and program of action below as a way of repaying the debt stock.

From the above we conclude the following:

1- The loan that Iraq negotiated in 2016 is a big gain for Iraq, as this is one of the loans given by the IMF to countries with little interest with a grace period of 3 years to repay, which is positive and serves the Iraqi interest and does not burden the Iraqi government with its fiscal policy.

2- This loan contributed to the evaluation of government performance by following a policy and road map that forced it to abide by the terms of the Fund, which reduced the corruption that usually accompanies any financial policy in the country.

3- The loans granted by international institutions such as the Fund and the World Bank have better results than those granted by states or their agencies, and the difference comes in terms of interest and commitment, which differ in application, the interest is high in the loans of countries and the obligation is non-existent, while interest is lower in IMF and World Bank loans and the road map is strong.

Recommendations and program of action

It is also known that foreign and domestic loans to Iraq amounted to more than \$131 billion in the current situation, which in itself requires a comprehensive development strategy and a sustainable and diversified investment program, and to implement this program we are developing the following roadmap:

1- Political parties in Iraq should move away from economic decision as a first step to economic and financial reform and put confidence in the elected Iraqi government.

2- The establishment of a special fund in which money is placed on the financial differences in oil prices, as it is known that the budget law determines the price of a barrel of oil at a minimum of its real price and the difference reaches more than 15 dollars from the real price and by calculation we multiply 15 dollars in the daily export rate of oil three million per month. We can commit the government to putting it in this proposed fund and be independent to be calculated and its capital set when the next budget is drawn.

With this capital, the following can be achieved:

a) These funds can be disposed of by repaying loans in the form of creditors' defenses, without affecting the state budget.

(b) It is possible to invest in production projects that increase the profits of this fund and is the best option.

C. Part of the subsequent budget deficit could be filled by this fund instead of recourse to loans.

Therefore, the government's decision to extend the period of the period of the year to the date of the first meeting of the General Staff committee is to be completed by the date of the meeting. Thus, it eases the burden on the investment budget and diversifies its projects.

3- Taking advantage of the differences in the exchange rates between the dinar and the dollar as it is known that the Central Bank presents the dollar at a price of approximately 1182 and is sold in the markets between 1120-1124 i.e. a difference of approximately \$3-5 from the central bank rate, and with a daily average of 150-200 million dollars a day we get The difference of 450,000 dollars per month is 13,500,000 and when it strikes in one year we get 162 million dollars that can be added to the proposed fund, rather than taken over by the corrupt.

4- Making use of the money hoarded by citizens in their homes, as these funds are estimated at 40 trillion dinars by employing them in various projects through banks, and the phenomenon of cash hoarding is present in many developing countries, including Iraq, i.e. citizens hoard their money at home outside Bank credit, which is a deduction from the income cycle that is completed in banking institutions interested in raising funds, and there are two reasons why citizens do not invest in banks. The first is the inability of these banks to interact with citizens because of traditional social customs and traditions in society, such as fear of being robbed by banks, for example, the weakness of the banking structure, which contributes to the non-promotion of the culture of citizen investment in banks, and therefore there is a situation of hesitation and fear of investing money. In banks and banks, both government and private. Investment in banks and banks is subject to real guarantees for the citizen and facilitate the withdrawal of his funds and the operation of those funds by banks and banks within the economic cycle, and then their ability to lend within reference loans and this is what moves the market, that

promote and spread a culture of investment in banks and urged Citizens on savings will raise the liquidity rates in banks, especially moving loans towards their beneficiaries and reducing the country's need for external loans.

5- Activating the role of selling bonds and investment certificates to complete strategic, vital and service projects that are funded by citizens and the private sector, as Egypt did when it raised the issue of the construction of the new Suez Canal (Renaissance Project) when it offered to sell investment certificates to collect 60 billion Egyptian pounds, with interest 12% annual and already EGP 61 billion of these certificates were collected in just 4 days from August 15-19, 2014.

6- The establishment of a sovereign fund for Iraq (which are investment funds owned by states but not under the ministries of finance or central banks and most of its resources come from the revenues of raw materials, mainly oil, the aim is to manage and invest part of the state's fiscal surpluses according to a profitable business plan in operations Long-term investment outside of countries of origin.)

From the foregoing, it can be said that the Iraqi government can do these proposals and adopt them as programs in providing solutions for economic development, debt repayment and the national interest of Iraq. It should be noted that we have developed this sequence of proposals to be a serial program starting number (1) which is to separate corruption from the economy and then find financial wealth as capital through number (2) and then increase the funds through (3) and then maximize them in investments through (4) and (5) and then find a strategic project Sustainable through (6). Only one or two paragraphs can also be relied upon as a minimum solution and adopted as a program that contributes to the Iraqi national interest.

References:

A fact sheet, imf lending, issued by the International Monetary Fund, electronic version, p. 1, published on the link:

<https://www.imf.org/~media/Files/Factsheets/Arabic/howlenda.ashx>

Abeer Ali Nasser, Salem AwadHadi, The Role of Fiscal Policy Instruments to Reduce the State Budget Deficit on the Terms of the International Monetary Fund, Journal of Accounting and Financial Studies, Higher Institute of Accounting and Financial Studies, University of Baghdad, Volume 14, Issue 48, Baghdad, 2019, p. 5.

IMF Annual Report 2018, Towards a Common Future, p. 44, posted on the Internet at:

<https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/ar/2018/eng/assets/pdf/imf-annual-report-2018-ar.pdf>

Credit Readiness Agreement 1952: A short-term to medium-term assistance to countries facing short-term balance of payments problems, but its terms are the adoption of policies that provide confidence in the possibility of resolving balance of payments problems in a member country within a reasonable period of time. For more see: IMF Annual Report 2018, source already mentioned, p. 48.

Flexible Credit Line 2009: A flexible tool in the context of credit segments to address all problems related to both potential and actual balance of payments needs. For more see the IMF's 2018 annual report, already mentioned, p. 48.

Prevention and Liquidity Line 2011: A tool for countries with peaceful economic fundamentals and policies, ranging from one to two years. For more see: IMF Annual Report 2018, source already mentioned, p. 48.

Extended Fund Facility 1974: Longer-term assistance to support structural reforms in member states to address long-term balance of payments problems. For more see: IMF Annual Report 2018, reference already mentioned, p. 48.

Fast Finance Tool 2011: Rapid financial assistance for all member countries facing pressing balance of payments needs, direct purchases without the need for a full program or reviews. For more see the IMF's 2018 annual report, a reference already mentioned in p. 48.

Alaa Abdul Hamid, for economic reform - with references to Iraq, Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences, Faculty of Administration and Economics, Baghdad University, No. 107, vol. 24, 2018, Baghdad, p. 504.

Ibid, p. 506.

The imf's official website, Special Drawing Rights, was published on 30 December 2016 at: <https://www.imf.org/ar/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2016/08/01/14/51/Special-Drawing-Right-SDR>

Yasser Al-Hawish, Special Drawing Rights Concept, Reality and Future, Damascus University Journal of Economic and Legal Sciences, Faculty of Law, Damascus University, Volume 30, Issue 2, Damascus, 2014. P. 13-15.

The imf's official website, Special Drawing Rights, was published on 30 December 2016 at: <https://www.imf.org/ar/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2016/08/01/14/51/Special-Drawing-Right-SDR>

Yasser al-Hawish, aforementioned reference, p. 17.

The IMF's official website, Special Drawing Rights, was published on 30 December 2016 at: <https://www.imf.org/ar/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2016/08/01/14/51/Special-Drawing-Right-SDR>

The IMF's official website, Special Drawing Rights, was published on 30 December 2016 at: <https://www.imf.org/ar/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2016/08/01/14/51/Special-Drawing-Right-SDR>

Al Bayan Center for Studies and Planning, No. 16/225, 2016, p. 4. Posted on the link: <http://www.bayancenter.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/98987600.pdf>

Medhat al-Quraishi, the International Monetary Fund loan to Iraq as a model, the new morning newspaper, electronic version, published on July 26, 2016 at the link: <https://newsabah.com/newspaper/91417>

IMF Report No. 16/225, Source Already Mentioned, p. 6.

Haidar Hussein Al-Touma, Credit Readiness Agreement and Governance of State Institutions, Al-Naba Information Network, article published on the Internet on January 1, 2017 at: <https://annabaa.org/arabic/authorsarticles/9292>

Hamed Abbas Mohammed, Economic Effects of Public Loans (Repayment Stage), Babylon University, Faculty of Law, article published on the official website of 21 December 2011 at: <http://www.uobabylon.edu.iq/uobColeges/lecture.aspx?fid=7&depid=1&lcid=24722>

Najib al-Azzawi, Measuring the Quality of the Government System, Model of Effective Government Performance in Iraq, Political Science Journal, Faculty of Political Science, Baghdad University, Issue 42, 2011, p. 5.

Hamed Abdul Hussein, Possible Causes and Effects of the IMF Loan to Iraq, Euphrates Center for Development and Strategic Studies, article published on the World Wide Web on May 30, 2016 at: <https://annabaa.org/arabic/authorsarticles/6547>

Author Information

Hayder Zuhair Jasim

University of Baghdad / Faculty of Engineering

h.alwaeli@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Dr. Saad Abdul Hussein Naama/

AL Kafeel University / Faculty of Law

saadabdulhussain@yahoo.com
